

HYPERTONIC SALINE ADMINISTRATION STIMULATES AVP RELEASE FROM
MAGNOCELLULAR CELLS, DECREASING PLAY BEHAVIOR

A project

submitted by

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to the
faculty of the Graduate School of
the University at Buffalo, The State University of New York
in fulfillment of the requirements for the
degree of

MASTER OF SCIENCE
Field of Neuroscience

Department of Biomedical Sciences
Jacobs School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences

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LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Social development is critical for an individual's overall health and wellbeing. Several neurodevelopmental disorders that impact social development arise during childhood or adolescence, e.g., Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD), Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) (Doernberg & Hollander, 2016), and Schizophrenia (Jones, Rodgers, Murray, & Marmot, 1994) (Hannah, Cathy, Dan, & David, 2012) . Uncovering the mechanisms that contribute to the prevention and treatment of various behavioral and cognitive disorders often incorporates the use of animal models such as rodents as they provide molecular similarity with humans and mimic numerous diseases found within us (Smith, Bolton, & Dwinell, 2019).

Social play is an ideal behavior to study social development in animals. It is an evolutionarily conserved behavior exhibited in most mammals that have been studied (Bekoff, 1984; Eisenberg, 1981). Play behavior emerges during the juvenile stage in rats around postnatal day (P)18, peaks during early to mid-adolescence (~P35), and then declines thereafter (Panksepp, 1981). Play behavior can be assessed in rats by documenting frequencies and durations of behaviors such as attacks and pins (Paul, Probst, Brown, & de Vries, 2018).

The neural mechanisms regulating play behavior are yet to be understood. Studies indicate the involvement of arginine vasopressin (AVP) (Cheng, Taravosh-Lahn, & Delville, 2008). For example, injections of a vasopressin 1a receptor (V1aR) antagonist, Manning compound, into the anterior hypothalamus of juvenile male Syrian hamsters or the lateral ventricles of juvenile male rats, decreased play behavior, suggesting a stimulatory role for endogenous vasopressin (Veenema, Bredewold, & De Vries, 2013) . Similarly, male and female juvenile Brattleboro rats, which lack AVP throughout development due to a mutation in the AVP gene (Schmale et al., 1993; Fig. 1), exhibit decreased social behaviors including decreased social play ((Paul et al., 2016); Fig. 2). Under some conditions, however, AVP appears to be inhibitory. ICV injections of the Manning compound increase play behavior in juvenile female rats as do septal injections in juvenile male rats (Bredewold, Smith, Dumais, & Veenema, 2014; Veenema et al., 2013). Hence, the impact of AVP on play behavior can depend on sex of the subject, brain region manipulated, and type of manipulations (acute pharmacological manipulation vs. chronic genetic mutation).

AVP has been implicated in several neurodevelopmental disorders such as ASD, ADHD, and Schizophrenia (Bilgiç, Toker, & Uysal, 2016; Francis et al., 2016). Hence, research into its neural pathways and behavioral associations can further our knowledge in treatment of aforementioned disorders.

1.2 AVP INDUCED PLAY BEHAVIOR

Brattleboro rats can be a useful model to study the impact of chronic AVP-deficiency on development. Due to a single base pair deletion in exon 2 of the AVP gene, Brattleboro rats generate a mutated AVP prohormone that is trapped in the ER, thus preventing its systemic circulation ((Schmale, Bahnsen, & Richter, 1993); Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Representation of AVP translation in normal and Brattleboro rat. A precursor consisting of a signal peptide (SP), AVP hormone, neurophysin carrier protein (NPH), and a glycopeptide (CP) is encoded for by the three exons, resulting in synaptic release of AVP from neurohypophyseal axons (Bichet, 1994; Bienemann et al., 2003). This prohormone is modified inside vesicles prior to its transportation to the posterior pituitary, where it is stored till its synaptic secretion. In a Brattleboro rat, the resultant mutated AVP prohormone is not properly processed by the endoplasmic reticulum, thus preventing the production of functional AVP (Schmale et al., 1993).

Adolescent Brattleboro rats exhibit an atypical social behavior profile characterized by decreased social play behaviors and an increase in huddling compared to their wild-type counterparts that have normal vasopressin production and secretion ((Paul et al., 2016); Fig. 2). While these experiments indicate a role for vasopressin in juvenile social behavior, they cannot determine the pathway by which AVP exerts its effects.

Fig. 2. Social behaviors and Play behaviors exhibited by Brattleboro rats in comparison to those seen in Het and WT. (Paul et al., 2016)

1.3 ARGININE VASOPRESSIN PATHWAYS

AVP employs several pathways to regulate behavioral and physiological functions including circadian rhythms, water balance, stress, autonomic function and social behavior. Cell bodies are located in the supraoptic nucleus of the hypothalamus (SON), paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus (PVN), suprachiasmatic nucleus of the hypothalamus, medial amygdala (MeA) and the bed nucleus stria terminalis (BNST), with AVP projections dispersed throughout the brain ((de Vries & Miller, 1998); Fig 3). The water balance circuit consists of magnocellular neurons of the PVN and SON projecting their AVP fibers towards the neurohypophysis (VRIES, CRENSHAW, & AL-SHAMMA, 1992).

Fig. 3. Vasopressin pathways (de Vries & Miller, 1998). Circadian circuit originates in parvocellular cells in the suprachiasmatic nucleus of the hypothalamus (SCN), with projections extending toward the paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus (PVN), medial preoptic area (mp), organum vasculosum of the lamina terminalis (ovlt) and the lateral habenula (lh). Known for its involvement in displaying social behaviors, steroid-sensitive, sexually dimorphic projections from the bed nucleus of stria terminalis (BNST) and medial amygdala (MA) project towards the olfactory tubercle (to), lateral septum (ls), lh, central grey (cg), dorsal raphe nucleus (dr), locus coeruleus (lc) and the hippocampus (hip). Furthermore, the water balance circuit, stemming from the SCN, SON and PVN, project toward the MA, dorsal vagal complex (dvc) and nucleus ambiguus (amb).

1.4 MAGNOCELLULAR CELLS AND ITS AXON COLLATERALS

Magnocellular cells in the SON and PVN projecting their axons towards the posterior pituitary, synthesize the majority of the AVP (Poulain & Wakerley, 1982). One of the key functions of AVP is to maintain blood osmolality. Plasma osmolality (Posm) ranges from 285 to 292 mmol/kg (Dunn, Brennan, Nelson, & Robertson, 1973). Hyperosmolality of the blood triggers osmoreceptors present within the subfornical organ (SFO), the organum vasculosum of the lamina terminalis (OVLT) (Thrasher & Keil, 1987), and the median preoptic nucleus (mPON). These osmoreceptors, which lie in the anteroventral third ventricle (AV3V) of the hypothalamus (Osaka, Yamashita, & Koizumi, 1988), further regulate AVP release via a cholinergic pathway, linking inputs on osmolality, blood volume and blood pressure from osmoreceptors to PVN and SON (Sladek & Joynt, 1979). Upon excitation, action potentials reach the neuroendocrine terminals of the magnocellular cells, resulting in the release of AVP into the peripheral circulatory system (Dunn et al., 1973). AVP then travels through the circulatory system to reach the kidneys, where its actions are antidiuretic, facilitating the fusion of aquaporin 2 channels with the luminal membrane of the distal convoluted tubule (DCT), which facilitates water reabsorption in the kidneys, which in turn affects the blood volume (Wilson, Miranda, & Knepper, 2013).

Fig. 4. Pathophysiological role of AVP (Ishikawa & Schrier, 2003)

Osmotic activation, triggered upon injecting hypertonic saline intra-peritoneally and intra-venously, stimulates the release of AVP from the neuroendocrine terminals within the posterior pituitary (as discussed above), but also from dendrites surrounding the SON. After ip or iv administration, an increase AVP was detected in the blood and in the tissue surrounding the SON, but the central response within the SON was delayed and occurred when blood levels of AVP were returning to basal levels (Ludwig, Callahan, Neumann, Landgraf, & Morris, 1994). Upon ip and iv administration, an immediate axonal release of AVP with peak blood levels detected 30-60 minutes post injection. Dendritic release within the SON, however, peaked between 2.5 hours post administration ((Ludwig et al., 1994); Fig. 5). This allows one to separate the effects of peripheral and central actions of AVP after a systemic hypertonic challenge. For example, testing behavior 2-3 h post-injection will coincide with elevated AVP within the brain, but not the periphery.

Fig. 5. (A) AVP release after ip (B) AVP release post iv administration; ■ AVP; □ OT
left; Plasma Na⁺ levels post ip and iv hypertonic saline injections causes immediate dialysate peptidyl release. Behaviors can be observed as early as 30 min after the injection
right; Central peptidyl release in the SON occurs after AVP levels have returned to their basal levels. Behaviors are observable 2.5-3.5 hrs after iv/ip administration

AVP, along with other neuropeptides, can be released from dendrites as well as axon terminals. Hence, stimulation of the SON and PVN results in release of AVP both in the peripheral circulatory system, from the neuroendocrine terminals, and in the brain, from dendrites. One of the advantages of a dendritic release is its role in optimizing neuronal firing activity upon osmotic stimulation. In fact, research indicates that stimulation of NMDA receptor in an AVP neuron triggered a dendritic release of AVP enough to depolarize and evoke excitatory responses within the neighboring neurons ((Son et al., 2013); Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. NMDA-R excitation resulted in a 5 sec delayed depolarization of presympathetic neurons. (Son et al., 2013)

Magnocellular AVP neurons display numerous axon collaterals that branch out into various brain areas thus influencing social and affective behaviors. Located in the hypothalamus, the EV16 neuron displays an increase in spiking rates upon hypertonic saline administration (Fig. 7A). Amongst the 5th generation dendrites (that branch all the way till the third ventricle; 3V) emerging from the soma of EV16 (located in the lateral division of the paraventricular nucleus, (PaLM), two collaterals: one, C2 bound for stria medullaris (sm) had ended its course in the LHb, while the other branched out towards the fornix. Another axon chartered a route along the PVN and culminating at the SCN (Fig. 7C4).

Fig. 7. (A) Firing patterns as observed in EV16 neuron; **red** indicates spiking after administering hypertonic solution while **blue** marks the basal irregular rhythms. **(C4)** Axonal collaterals projecting towards the LHb

Similarly, three other neurons, namely EV40, VH52 and MM15, located in the posterior paraventricular nucleus (PaPo), respond to hypertonic saline administrations by increasing their firing rates. While EV40 projects secondary axons toward the tract of Greving and the optical tract, along with processes extending towards the amygdala and the fornix (Fig. 8), the VH52 had collaterals branching out to the ventral palladium, stria medullaris, fornix, ventral palladium, internal capsule and the tract of Greving (Fig. 9). Additionally, MM15 also had projections traveling to the tract of Greving and to the fornix (Fig. 10). Thus, these visualizations concur that the magnocellular hypothalamic AVP neurons are not only responsible for water balance but also have axonal projections toward the social behavior circuitry.

Fig. 8. (C1) Soma of the neuron located in the PaPo; EV40 neuron is depicted to extend its axonal processes towards the fornix, central and medial amygdala and the optical tract

Fig. 9. (C1) AVP-IR neurons; green traces indicate beaded dendritic processes in the PVN (C2) Pearl-like axonal branches in the lateral preoptic area (C3-C5) Axonal segments in the fornix, internal capsule and stria medullaris. (Hernandez et al., 2015)

Fig. 10. Dendritic and axonal projections of MM15 neuron

1.5 OSMOTIC CHALLENGE, AVP ACTIVATION AND THIRST-ASSOCIATED BEHAVIORS

Thirst, fundamental for maintaining homeostasis, is regulated by PVN and SON nuclei. Water deprivation causes an overexpression of the aforementioned AVP magnocellular neurons. Dehydration can cause electrolyte and water imbalance, triggering an osmotic stress response. Activation of GABAergic interneurons of the lateral habenula (LHb) is found to regulate stress coping strategies like freezing and immobility behaviors (Pobbe & Zangrossi, 2008).

To assess fear processing and behavioral despair, rats were subjected to water deprivation for 24 hours (WD24), followed by analyses of their freezing vs. rearing/climbing and immobility vs climbing behaviors when presented to a predator such as a cat and put through a forced swimming test (FST), respectively (Zhang, Hernandez, Vazquez-Juarez, Chay, & Barrio, 2016). WD24 causes about 3% increase in blood osmolality and up to a 7-fold increase in AVP concentration (Dunn et al., 1973).

These aforementioned behaviors are being documented in ((Zhang et al., 2016); Fig. 11 A-D). The WD24 rats showed a reduction in freezing behaviors and a significant increase in rearing and climbing behaviors (Fig. 11 A,B). Moreover, the FST results indicate a decrease in immobility and a remarkable increase in climbing behaviors (Fig. 11 C,D). Furthermore, in the elevated plus maze test, the rats were tested for locomotor control, which depicted a decrease in the amount of time spent in open arms, indicative of WD24 rats being cautious of their movements in open arms (Fig. 11 E). These results indicate that thirst can upregulate motivational behaviors (rearing/climbing) alongside a reducing passive stress coping behavior (immobility/freezing).

Fig. 11. (A)(B) Active (Rearing) and Passive (Freezing) behaviors were observed in control and WD-24 rats upon exposure to a predator. (C)(D) Reduced immobility and high climbing behaviors observed in WD-24. (E) The amount of time spent in open arms in a WD-24 rat, when compared to control .

HYPOTHESIS

Experiments with Brattleboro rats have documented the effects of AVP on play behaviors. A single bp mutation in the AVP gene can pause its overall production and release ((Schmale et al., 1993); Fig. 1), which corresponds to a decrease in social behaviors, particularly play behaviors observed in juvenile rats ((Paul et al., 2016); Fig. 2).

Under an osmotic challenge, when the body is exposed to internal stressors, AVP is released peripherally and centrally, via a dendritic and an axonal release ((Ludwig et al., 1994); Fig. 5).

Furthermore, active and passive stress coping behaviors are directly affected by water deprivation, where the former is upregulated while the latter is documented to display decreased counts ((Zhang et al., 2016); Fig. 11 A-D).

Hence, this study would like to investigate the effects of AVP release from magnocellular cells on play behaviors in rats; AVP is expected to cause an increase in play behaviors. I conducted an initial test of this hypothesis by stimulating AVP release from magnocellular cells via a hypertonic saline administration and assessed whether this manipulation increased play behaviors.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

3.1 ANIMALS AND HOUSING

Male and female Long-Evans rats arrived at 21 days of age (Harlan, Indianapolis, IN) and were housed in same-sex pairs in plastic cages (44 cm x 22.5 cm x 20.5 cm). Room lights were set to 12 hr light/12 hr dark cycle, and an ambient temperature of 23°C was maintained. At 30-40 days of age, rats were injected IP with varying doses of hypertonic saline (1 molar (M) or 3.5M) or normal saline (0.9%; control animals) under isoflurane anesthesia. A second control group was not injected with any substance (None) in order to assess potential effects of the injection procedure. Two hours after injection, rats were tested in the Social Interaction Test. Water bottles were removed at the time of the injection and were returned to the animals after behavior testing. All procedures were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee at the University at Buffalo, SUNY, and were in accordance with the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory animals.

3.2 SOCIAL INTERACTION TESTS

Eight hours before testing, rats were separated. Single housing prior to testing increases play behavior (Panksepp 1981). Rats of the same age, sex, and treatment were then paired as playmates in a plastic arena for 20 min. Behavior tests were recorded by a video camera mounted above the arena. Social behaviors were scored using BORIS software by an experimenter unaware of group assignments. Scored behaviors included:

- Play behaviors – play attacks (rat lunges towards playmate and may chase said playmate) and pins (rat stands above playmate with the latter in a supine position or on its side)
- Social approach (rat sniffs playmate)
- Tail grab (rat clutches playmate's tail and pulls)
- Aggression (rat displays aggressive behaviors like biting the rear and pulling it)
- Huddling (rat maintains physical contact with playmate and remains relatively motionless for several seconds)

3.3 STATISTICAL ANALYSES

Behavioral measures were assessed using ANOVA with sex (male vs female) and with treatment (no injection, normal saline, 1M saline and 3.5 M saline) as independent variables. Significant main effects were further assessed with pair-wise post-hoc comparisons with the Tukey HSD correction. Significance was assumed when $P < 0.05$. All statistical procedures were conducted using SPSS.

RESULTS

There was a significant main effect of injection on the duration of total play (Fig. 12; $P < 0.05$, main effect of injection, ANOVA). The main effect of sex and the sex/injection interaction were not significant ($P > 0.05$, ANOVA). Post-hoc test reveals that rats receiving injections of 3.5 M saline played less than all other groups ($P < 0.05$, Tukey HSD); none of the other groups differed from each other ($P > 0.05$, Tukey HSD). Social Approach exhibited a similar overall pattern, however, was not significant (Fig. 13; $P > 0.05$, main effects of injection, sex, and sex/injection interaction, ANOVA). Huddling also differed across injection groups (Fig. 14; $P < 0.05$, main effect of injection, ANOVA; $P > 0.05$, main effect of sex and sex/injection interaction, ANOVA). For huddling, however, rats receiving injections of 3.5 M saline huddled more than those in other groups ($P < 0.05$, Tukey HSD); remaining groups didn't differ from each other ($P > 0.05$, Tukey HSD).

Fig. 12. Injections of high concentrations of hypertonic saline decrease social play behavior. Mean (\pm s.e.) duration of total play behavior of female (black bars) and male (gold bars) Long Evans rats receiving IP injections of normal saline (0.9%; Norm), 1M hypertonic saline, or 3.5M hypertonic saline 2 h prior to testing; animals not receiving injections (None) were included to assess possible confounds of the injection procedure. * Indicates decreased total play duration of rats receiving 3.5M saline injections compared to all other groups ($P < 0.05$, Tukey HSD).

Fig. 13. Hypertonic saline injections did not significantly impact social approach behavior. Mean (\pm s.e.) duration of social approach behavior of female (black bars) and male (gold bars) Long Evans rats receiving IP injections of normal saline (0.9%; Norm), 1M hypertonic saline, or 3.5M

hypertonic saline 2 h prior to testing; animals not receiving injections (None) were included to assess possible confounds of the injection procedure.

Fig. 14. Injections of high concentrations of hypertonic saline increase huddling behavior. Mean (\pm s.e.) duration huddling behavior of female (black bars) and male (gold bars) Long Evans rats receiving IP injections of normal saline (0.9%; Norm), 1M hypertonic saline, or 3.5M hypertonic saline 2 h prior to testing; animals not receiving injections (None) were included to assess possible confounds of the injection procedure. * Indicates increases huddling behavior rats receiving injections of rats receiving 3.5M saline injections compared to all other groups ($P < 0.01$, Tukey HSD).

There was no effect of sex or injection on the duration of aggressive behavior (Fig. 15; $P > 0.05$, main effect of sex, injection and sex/injection, ANOVA). It should be noted that levels of aggression were very low (the mean duration of aggression for all the groups was less than 10 seconds).

Fig. 15. Hypertonic saline injections did not significantly impact aggression. Mean (\pm s.e.) duration of aggressive behavior of female (black bars) and male (gold bars) Long Evans rats receiving IP injections of normal saline (0.9%; Norm), 1M hypertonic saline, or 3.5M hypertonic saline 2 h prior to testing; animals not receiving injections (None) were included to assess possible confounds of the injection procedure.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study hypothesized an increase in play behavior upon AVP release, however, the results indicate a decrease in play behavior at the highest saline concentration (3M hypertonic saline). Huddling behavior, sometimes described as a side-by-side contact (Ramos et al., 2013), observed here as a physical contact maintained with a playmate, was increased in animals receiving the highest concentrations of hypertonic saline. Aggressive behaviors were not impacted by saline treatment and were relatively low in all groups.

The decrease in play behaviors is in stark contrast to our hypothesis and to findings in Brattleboro rats and intracerebroventricular V1AR antagonist injection studies in males (Lukas & Wöhr, 2015; Paul et al., 2016; Veenema et al., 2013). As mentioned in the Introduction, however, vasopressin has also been suggested to play an inhibitory role under some conditions (Veenema et al., 2013). This raises the possibility that magnocellular vasopressin cells are responsible for the inhibitory actions of AVP on play behavior seen in select contexts. However, other non-AVP effects of hypertonic saline must also be considered (see below).

With regard to the huddling/adjacent lying, our results are in line with those reported by Ramos et al. (2013), who found that peripheral injections of AVP increased adjacent lying, an effect that was reversed by a V1AR antagonist (SR49059). (Ramos et al., 2013). In this study, we did note sickness behaviors (hunched positions, seated close to playmate often with their bodies touching each other, piloerection and lack of mobility) in some animals after hypertonic saline treatment. These sickness behaviors were mostly observed in animals treated with 3.5M hypertonic saline solution, suggests that the behavioral effects could be due to a generalized aversive experience rather than to AVP release. This could account for the decrease in active behaviors and increase in huddling noted in the experiment. Hence, conclusions on the role of magnocellular AVP in social behaviors remains unknown. Future studies will need manipulate magnocellular AVP without inducing sickness behavior side effects. One could mimic the water deprivation studies that demonstrated changes to affective behaviors in adult rats (Zhang et al. 2016; see discussion in Introduction) or perhaps, assess different time points after 1M saline injections, which did not induce obvious sickness behaviors.

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